

Forecasting Trends in Cloud-Edge Computing: Unleashing the Power of Attention Mechanisms

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Abstract—In the face of expanding digital landscapes, cloud-edge computing infrastructures struggle with an ever-increasing demand for real-time data management. This demand has a direct impact on the energy consumption of cloud-edge networks, which has spiked dramatically, stressing the need for accurate time-series forecasting. As conventional machine learning models encounter difficulties in predicting volatile workloads, *attention mechanisms* have emerged thanks to their capability of capturing long-range dependencies. This article pioneers the exploration of attention mechanisms for time-series forecasting in cloud-edge environments, particularly focusing on a promising low-complexity attention mechanism (i.e., informer model). Through comprehensive discussions and experimental validations, we demonstrate that informers significantly outperform traditional models in the prediction accuracy of compute workload forecasting. The outcome of this work not only highlights the importance of attention mechanisms in cloud-edge scenarios but also paves the way for future optimizations, ultimately aiming at reducing the environmental impact of digital growth.

Index Terms—Zero-touch, AI, LSTM, Transformers, Informers, Edge Computing, Time-series Forecasting, Deep Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Can you imagine a world where telecommunication networks anticipate every need, optimizing resources seamlessly in real-time? As the digital realm continues to expand, the demand for instantaneous, efficient, and accurate data management grows exponentially. Cloud and edge computing have revolutionized data management and computational resource exploitation, though it does come with a cost in terms of energy. Notably, during 2019, the daily energy consumption of cloud data centers and edge networks was equivalent to the energy released by approximately 74 Hiroshima atomic bombs, a figure that is constantly rising [1]. Leveraging machine learning for workload forecasting enhances resource utilization and significantly reduces energy consumption, thereby lowering the carbon footprint.

Envision a bustling smart city, where traffic lights adapt on-the-fly to traffic flows, energy grids foresee spikes in usage, and telecom networks anticipate user behavior to fine-tune bandwidth. To make this vision a reality, it is essential to provide precise predictions for these factors [2], [3]. However, the challenge is immense, as the dynamic nature of cloud-edge networks requires a fine-tuned balance between demand and available resources. Any misalignment, such as insufficient or excessive provisioning, can directly impact service quality and operational costs.

The accuracy of machine learning in forecasting is crucial for managing complexities, optimizing resource allocation, and ensuring high service quality [4], [5]. In edge computing, models with low inference times are highly valued for their ability to enable quick decision-making, ensure optimal performance on resource-constrained devices, and enhance energy efficiency [6]. Commonly forecasted sequences include time-series data such as user access patterns, energy consumption rates, and server load demand, among others.

Sequence forecasting models have evolved to better handle time-based patterns. Initially, Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) based models were the go-to choice, specifically designed to handle sequential data patterns. However, their performance often suffered due to a major drawback: a declining memory of recalling previous data. In straightforward terms, it is like reading a long book and, by the end, struggling to remember the details from the beginning — a problem known as the vanishing/exploding gradient issue [7].

Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs) made significant progress in capturing patterns in extended sequences. LSTMs introduced multiple direct information pathways, minimizing information loss over long sequences. However, LSTMs still fall short in accurately predicting the volatile workloads in cloud-edge environments [5]. Recognizing these limitations, researchers added *attention mechanisms* to enhance the capabilities of LSTMs. The attention mechanism enables a model to focus selectively on parts of the input sequence, identifying and weighing the relevance of different data points. By considering the relationship between all pairs of data points, regardless of their distance in the sequence, attention mechanisms can detect complex patterns and dependencies that might be missed by other models. With this enhancement, LSTMs equipped with attention mechanisms showed enhanced performance in handling long-range dependencies and volatile workloads.

The development of hybrid LSTM-attention models paved the way for a revolutionary change: the advent of the transformer architecture, which solely relies on attention mechanisms to assess the relative importance of all input data points [8]. The key advantage of transformers lies in their ability to process input sequences in parallel, in contrast with the sequential approach of RNN-based models such as LSTMs, a feature that significantly enhances computational efficiency. However, their high time complexity limits their suitability for the extended datasets common in time-series forecasting. To

tackle this issue, *sparse attention* emerged as an alternative attention mechanism, which features fewer connections than the *full attention* model in the original transformer architecture, offering a more streamlined approach [9].

This article makes a pivotal contribution to the application of time-series forecasting in the cloud-edge computing domain. Our contribution is threefold: First, we explore the state-of-the-art and the evolution in time-series forecasting, setting the foundation for understanding current challenges and opportunities in this field. Second, we delve into the role of attention mechanisms, highlighting their benefits and introducing the informer architecture, i.e., a novel *sparse-attention* approach that significantly enhances forecasting in cloud-edge computing environments. Finally, we demonstrate the practical application of informers through various case studies and provide comprehensive guidelines for their integration, design, and deployment, thereby offering a roadmap for leveraging informers in the cloud-edge continuum.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section II presents the background and the evolution of machine learning in time-series forecasting. Section III offers an in-depth analysis of both full and sparse attention mechanisms. Section IV provides use cases in the cloud-edge domain, along with selective proof-of-concept experimental results that demonstrate the benefits of informer models in specific scenarios. The article concludes by summarizing key insights and suggesting future research directions.

II. MACHINE LEARNING ON TIME-SERIES FORECASTING

In this section, we delve into the history of machine learning evolution in the time-series forecasting challenge.

A. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)

The ARIMA model [4] in forecasting uses AutoRegression (AR), Integration (I), and Moving Average methods (MA). This methodology is appropriate for analyzing time-series data, as it effectively captures trends through integration while leveraging historical values and previous forecasting errors. ARIMA has become a popular choice in areas like resource management thanks to its ability to provide reasonably accurate forecasts. However, it is essential to recognize some of its challenges and limitations. The ARIMA model, while efficient for quick inference, faces challenges when training on large datasets. Additionally, it may struggle to effectively capture inter-dependencies between correlated time-series, showing better performance with singular time-series. Furthermore, the model's accuracy can be adversely affected by high levels of noise or significant data fluctuations.

B. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)

RNNs hold a respected place in the history of time-series forecasting. These networks offer a new way to handle sequential data that changes over time, a domain where classical models such as ARIMA were challenged by their own assumptions of data stationarity and linearity.

A key feature of RNNs is their ability to loop information back into the network. These unique information paths let them

share information across different points in time, empowering RNNs with the ability to process sequential data. This particular attribute made RNNs an ideal candidate for time-series forecasting.

However, RNNs encounter the vanishing gradient problem [7] during backpropagation. This issue can limit their effectiveness in learning from long data sequences. Backpropagation involves updating the neural network's weights by propagating the gradient of the error function backwards. When the gradient diminishes excessively, it impedes the network's learning capacity, especially for modeling long-range dependencies.

C. Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs)

LSTMs, a subclass of RNNs, were engineered to address the vanishing gradient problem that affects conventional RNNs. LSTMs use information gates to choose what time-related information to keep or toss. These gates enable them understand patterns over longer time periods in time-series data. These innovations allow LSTMs to outperform traditional models like ARIMA and basic RNNs in time-series data predictions.

Fig. 1 (a) provides a high-level overview of the LSTM architecture [7]. Key characteristics include: **Input Sequence Length** ($n = \dim(\mathbf{x})$): The number of historical data points used as input. **Number of Layers** (L): Indicates network depth, with more layers enabling the learning of more abstract features but increasing training complexity. **Feedforward Network Dimension** (d_{ff}): Determines the vector size of the LSTM's hidden state (\mathbf{h}), affecting model capacity and complexity. **Prediction Sequence Length** ($\dim(\mathbf{y})$): LSTMs output the next data point, but using predicted data points as inputs can create a sequence of predictions. **Training**: At each time step, the LSTM processes an input and updates its hidden and cell states to make a prediction. The training loss is calculated by comparing the prediction to the true value and network weights adjusted through backpropagation to improve accuracy.

LSTMs exhibit several inherent limitations:

- **Sequential processing**: Inability to fully exploit hardware optimized for parallel computations.
- **Limited long-range forecasting**: Challenges in accurately predicting over extended temporal horizons due to the vanishing gradient problem.
- **Reduced inference speed**: Decline in throughput for long output sequence lengths due to sequential processing.

In summary, LSTMs are computationally intensive and prone to overfitting because of their architecture. The sequential nature of LSTMs blocks their efficiency on parallel hardware, such as graphics processing units (GPUs), creating challenges for real-time applications in edge and cloud computing. Regarding long-term forecasting, LSTMs face constraints, as their error rates level off with increasing prediction horizon, indicating limitations in capturing long-range dependencies [10]. As a consequence, this leads to lower performance in longer-term forecasts. In scenarios requiring rapid inference, such as edge computing, LSTMs are suboptimal, particularly with lengthy input sequences.

Fig. 1. LSTM processes data sequentially with an LSTM cell at each point, while a transformer outputs complete sequences at once. High-level illustration of both architectures with hyperparameters. Common hyperparameters: feedforward network dimension d_{ff} , input sequence length $n = \dim(\mathbf{x})$ and prediction sequence length $\dim(\mathbf{y})$.

III. THE POWER OF ATTENTION

This section explores the evolution of attention mechanisms, comparing the original full attention in transformers with the more computationally efficient sparse attention. Lastly, we introduce the informer architecture, which incorporates sparse attention as one of its key components.

A. Transformers: The Dawn of the Attention Mechanism

The major breakthrough of transformers is their use of attention mechanisms alone, which sets them apart from the traditional approach of RNNs [8]. In RNNs, data is processed one step at a time, making it harder to capture relationships between distant points in a sequence [7]. Transformers, on the other hand, allow any two points in a sequence to connect directly, no matter how far apart they are. This is done through an attention mechanism that assigns different importance, or attention scores, to each connection based on how much one point influences another. This direct linking of points makes it easier for the model to understand long-range dependencies, leading to better performance, especially in tasks that require recognizing patterns across longer sequences [11].

Fig. 1 (b) illustrates a high-level overview of the transformer architecture. Key characteristics include: **Embedding Dimension** (d_{model}): This parameter defines the size of the vector space for input features, significantly affecting the model's ability to capture and represent complex relationships within the data. **Encoder and Decoder Blocks** (N_e, N_d): The transformer architecture utilizes multiple stacked layers in both the encoder and decoder components. These blocks enhance the model's capacity to learn intricate patterns. Encoder blocks transform input data into higher-level representations, while decoder blocks convert these representations into the desired output. Both types of blocks incorporate layers of attention mechanisms and feedforward networks, which are crucial for effectively processing and transforming the data.

Attention Heads (H): The model employs parallel attention mechanisms, allowing it to focus on different parts of the input simultaneously. This multi-head attention approach enables the model to capture various aspects of the input data concurrently. **Feedforward Network Dimension** (d_{ff}): This parameter determines the size of the feedforward network in each block, directly influencing the model's capacity to process and generate information. **Training**: Transformers process entire sequences simultaneously, enabling efficient parallelization and improving computational performance, especially when utilizing GPUs. During training, the network calculates the loss by comparing predicted sequences to true value sequences and adjusts its weights through backpropagation.

Nonetheless, it is also essential to note the negative aspects of transformers [10]:

- **High computational demand**: The fundamental operation of the attention mechanism, leads to a quadratic time complexity.
- **Memory bottleneck when dealing with long inputs**: When stacking encoder/decoder layers, the total memory usage becomes large, something that limits the model's scalability and its ability to handle long sequence inputs.
- **Inference time**: The decoding process is linear, reducing prediction speed for long sequences.

In the next section, we will explore how informers address these limitations and enhance performance for efficient long-sequence time-series forecasting.

B. Faster & Lighter Transformers: Sparse Attention as a Generic Solution

The initial transformer architecture, while strong in processing sequence data, faces challenges due to its quadratic time complexity. In the last few years, several efforts have been made towards tackling the time-complexity issue of

Fig. 2. A transformer using sparse attention to enhance computational efficiency.

the transformer architecture. Among many potential solutions, sparse transformers offer a more efficient alternative, using attention mechanisms that select the most influential previous data points to alleviate the complexity issue [9].

The nature of *sparse attention* is the selective scoring with a subset of data points or sequence elements. This mechanism reduces computational complexity from $O(n^2)$ to a more manageable level, such as $O(n \log n)$ or $O(n)$, depending on the sparsity pattern [9]. Fig. 2 illustrates an example of a sparse attention pattern. Note that several configurations can exist depending on the specific requirements of the application.

The sparse attention mechanism strikes a balance between computational efficiency and model performance. First, by strategically focusing on a subset of data points, it minimizes the quadratic time complexity associated with full attention, thereby enabling faster processing of sequences. This is especially critical for real-time applications that require latency within the 50 ms threshold [12], making sparse attention a viable solution in edge computing environments. Second, by carefully picking out important data points, sparse attention makes sure the model can still capture long-range connections between data points, which is a strong feature of the original transformer.

However, there are also hurdles to consider. The need for ample training data is a recurring theme when deploying advanced models, including sparse attention models. The large dataset issue could prove problematic in scenarios with limited data availability.

C. Informers: Specialized Sparse Attention Transformers for Time-Series Forecasting

Informers constitute a representative example of sparse attention mechanisms [9]. Chosen for their distinct architecture innovations, detailed in the next sections, they excel in efficiency and accuracy with extensive time-series data, typical in cloud-edge contexts. However, their suitability varies with each application's specific needs and limitations.

1) *Architectural Innovations*: The general architecture of the informer model is very similar to the transformer architecture which is shown in Fig. 1b. Consequently, the hyperparameters are equivalent. However, the informer includes several unique innovations that collectively enhance its performance [10]:

- **Sparse Attention**: Informers utilize a specialized sparse attention mechanism that enhances computational efficiency. By constructing a sparse matrix that retains only the most critical queries, the model focuses on the most relevant information while reducing computational complexity. This approach scales linearly with the logarithm of the sequence length, making it highly suitable for processing long sequences.
- **Attention Distilling**: In the context of sparse attention, where the attention matrix contains zeros, attention distilling improves memory efficiency even further. By eliminating these redundant entries, this technique reduces the amount of data processed in each layer. This allows the model to focus on the most important information while conserving memory resources.
- **Generative Style Decoder**: Traditional transformers generate forecasts in a sequential manner, producing one output at a time. In contrast, informers feature a generative-style decoder, enabling the output of an entire sequence in a single step. This accelerates the forecasting process significantly and allows more efficient parallelization.

In the next section, we will explore how informers address these limitations and enhance performance for efficient long-sequence time-series forecasting.

2) *Strengths and Weaknesses of Informers*: Informers come with two basic advantages: i) **efficiency**, as the sparse attention mechanism and the distilling processes offer a computational efficiency that is orders of magnitude better than transformers; and ii) **speed**, since the generative style decoder facilitates rapid inference, making informers highly effective in time-critical use cases, such as edge applications. On the other hand, their main drawback is the **implementation complexity**, as the specialized features and optimizations make the architecture complex to be implemented and fine-tuned.

D. A Comprehensive Look at Time-Series Forecasting Models

The evaluation of time-series forecasting models should not be limited to computational efficiency alone. As summarized in Table 1, different models offer varying strengths across metrics such as long-range memory, architectural advantages, and parallelization capabilities for effective GPU usage. For instance, while LSTMs are computationally efficient with $O(n)$ complexity, they struggle with long-range dependencies, unlike transformers and informers that excel in this area thanks to their attention mechanisms. Informers, in particular, offer an optimized trade-off, operating at $O(n \log n)$ complexity, which makes them highly effective for long sequences and real-time applications.

IV. APPLICATIONS OF THE INFORMER MODEL IN CLOUD-EDGE DOMAINS

This section outlines the applications of the informer model in cloud-edge domains, emphasizing its low inference time for rapid decision-making in resource-limited settings [6], [10]. Through proof-of-concept experiments, we demonstrate its potential in workload forecasting, while we also provide insights on other possible use cases in edge computing

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF TIME-SERIES FORECASTING MODELS.

Metric/Model	Informers	Transformers	LSTMs	Vanilla RNNs	ARIMA
Use GPUs Effectively	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Long Range Memory	Yes	Yes	Limited	No	No
Vanishing Gradient	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
Exploits Extended Inputs	Yes	Yes, inefficient	No	No	No
Inference Time	Very Fast	Slow	Fast	Fast	Slow
Time Complexity	$O(n \log n)$	$O(n^2)$	$O(n)$	$O(n)$	$O(n^2)$ to $O(n^3)$
Usage	Long-sequence	Mid-sequence	Short-sequence	Short-sequence	Time-series
Architecture	Sparse attention	Full attention	RNN	RNN	Statistical

scenarios. In addition, we present strategies for deploying, managing, and optimizing machine learning models in cloud-edge environments, aiming to enhance predictive analytics and efficiency across various applications.

A. Optimizing Workload Forecasting in Edge Computing: A Case Study

Efficient resource allocation is essential in both cloud and edge computing domains, especially within multi-provider environments (where services and resources are provided by multiple cloud or edge service providers) as demand patterns are highly unpredictable and fluctuate significantly [13]. Ineffective or slow resource allocation can lead to service disruptions, user dissatisfaction, and increased energy consumption. Effective workload prediction is crucial for timely resource provisioning, enabling systems to manage incoming requests with low latency and optimal resource utilization, thereby maintaining high service quality [5]. This is particularly critical in scenarios requiring prompt responses, such as real-time analytics, emergency services, and financial transactions [3].

In such environments, automatic configuration and deployment with resource scaling based on workload forecasting are vital [4]. This ensures resources are dynamically scaled, optimizing performance and efficiency across cloud-edge infrastructures. Dynamic changes in node capacity require prediction-driven optimizations. These enable proactive resource management and anticipatory adjustments, addressing the need for efficient resource scaling and self-regulation.

In this study, we compare informers with LSTMs and transformers using three metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). Our exploration employs the Google 2019 Cluster Trace dataset [13], aiming to highlight the potential of informers in enhancing resource allocation strategies within cloud-edge computing domains.

1) *Data Collection, Preprocessing and Training:* The dataset, recorded in May 2019, represents the average CPU utilization across a cluster of 10,000 machines. The data is sampled during 5-minute intervals, resulting in 8,928 data points for the entire month. The dataset is split into training (70%), test (20%), and validation (10%) sets. The data is subjected to normalization, and the training process is executed using NVIDIA A10 GPUs, specifically engineered to excel in AI-related workloads. Our experimental setup validates the informer’s performance in a heterogeneous environment,

characteristic of the edge-cloud continuum. The dataset includes diverse CPU and memory traces, mirroring real-world conditions. This diversity enhances the robustness and realism of our results, ensuring they represent the dynamic nature of modern cloud-edge systems.

2) *Hyperparameters:* Each hyperparameter set defines a unique model configuration for LSTMs (Fig. 1 (a)) and informers/transformers (Fig. 1 (b)). Grid search is employed to identify the optimal configuration by evaluating all hyperparameter combinations. Training hyperparameters are consistent for all models: input lengths $n = \{24, 48, 168, 360\}$, batch size = 24, learning rate = 1×10^{-4} , dropout rate = 0.1, loss function: MSE, epochs = 10, feedforward network dimension $d_{ff} = \{128, 512, 2048\}$.

Informers and Transformers Hyperparameters: Encoder blocks $N_e = \{2, 4, 6\}$, decoder blocks $N_d = 2$, attention heads $H = \{8, 16\}$, embedding dimension $d_m = 512$.

LSTMs Hyperparameters: Number of layers $L = \{2, 4, 6\}$.

During grid search, each combination of these hyperparameters is evaluated based on predefined metrics (RMSE and MAE) and the configuration with the best performance is selected for the respective model. The hyperparameter ranges are derived from the original codebases of [8] and [10].

3) Testing Performance:

Experiment 1 - Varying input and prediction sequence length: The input and prediction sequence lengths are set equal to each other. Fig. 3 shows that attention mechanisms (both informers and transformers) consistently outperform LSTMs across all sequence lengths. At specific input sequence lengths (i.e., 48, 168, and 360) the MSE improvement that attention mechanisms achieve over LSTMs is approximately 29%, 31%, and 31%, respectively. Notice that the performance of informers is slightly worse than transformers, as expected due to the sparse attention mechanism.

Additional metrics are considered to enhance model assessment. Transformers display superior precision, evidenced by the lowest average MAE (0.70098) and RMSE (0.86726). Informers are close contenders at low complexity with MAE (0.71350) and RMSE (0.88054). LSTMs, however, show lower accuracy, marked by higher MAE (0.87023) and RMSE (1.05292). The key finding from this experiment is that both sparse attention and full attention mechanisms exhibit comparable performance, outperforming LSTMs.

Experiment 2 - Fine-tuning for predicting GPU usage in a large cluster: We have fine-tuned the models for the specific

Fig. 3. Evaluating forecasting robustness: MSE across variable input sequence length and prediction horizons for all models.

task of predicting average CPU usage for a cluster of 10,000 machines. Specifically, we have fixed the prediction sequence length to 24. Fig. 4 provides a focused view on 5-minute interval predictions, highlighting the attention mechanism’s superiority during rapid demand shifts. Informers, while having a marginally higher MSE of 0.00071 compared to transformers 0.00061, achieve this with less complexity. Additionally, their MAE and RMSE values are competitively close, underscoring the informers performance despite their simpler architecture.

The LSTM is not able to capture the highly dynamic and complex workload pattern because it struggles with long-range dependency modeling due to the vanishing gradient problem. Compared to attention-based models that maintain a direct information path, enabling equal access to distant data points regardless of their separation in the sequence.

Fig. 5 illustrates the inference speed comparison over 1,000 measurements, highlighting informers’ superior efficiency with an average inference time of 0.1052 seconds, i.e., 43.2% faster than transformers at 0.1851 seconds. Additionally, the average time for training (22 measurements) reveals informers’ sparse attention mechanism to be 26.9% quicker, taking only 202.63 seconds compared to the 277.36 seconds required for full attention transformers.

Our findings highlight the effectiveness of informers in optimizing resource allocation for edge computing. Notably, they offer cost-effective training and inference, which are crucial considerations in the context of low-power, low-CPU edge network devices. These attributes are demonstrated by their performance on a relevant dataset.

B. Powering the Future: Next-Gen Predictive Models for Green Energy in Cloud-Edge Networks

Integrating renewable energy sources in cloud-edge computing is challenging due to their unpredictability [14]. Regional

Fig. 4. Comparing informer and LSTM Models on CPU Usage Forecasting.

Fig. 5. Training and inference time comparison for each model with 95% confidence intervals.

factors such as grid control, energy distribution, and data-sharing policies must be considered. Informers, with advanced predictive capabilities, can model these regional variations. By capturing grid strategies, predicting energy source fluctuations, and adhering to data-sharing policies, informers optimize resource allocation for adaptive energy management.

Informers can use historical data like solar radiance or wind patterns to forecast renewable energy availability. For example, solar-powered devices can predict limited sunlight periods, enhancing efficiency and sustainability. Integrating carbon intensity forecasts allows for dynamic task scheduling, minimizing the carbon footprint and enhancing sustainability.

C. Enhancing Failure Prediction and Anomaly Detection

Accurate predictions help providers recover from routine and extraordinary failures. Cloud-edge systems are complex, making failure detection crucial. Traditional methods often miss intricate patterns, such as scheduled tasks or interdependent node issues [15]. Informers excel at recognizing long-term dependencies and significant data points, allowing detection of subtle deviations signaling rare events. This provides timely insights for better resource management and

failure mitigation, ensuring system resilience and minimizing downtime.

Scaling anomaly detection while preserving data privacy is essential for managing increasing data volumes and complexity [4]. Generalization techniques train models on non-sensitive data, creating versatile models for private data. Using non-sensitive metrics like CPU and memory usage for anomaly detection avoids privacy concerns. Data anonymization further secures sensitive information. These strategies collectively enable effective, scalable, and privacy-preserving anomaly detection.

D. Generic Guidelines for Integration of Informers in the Cloud-Edge Continuum for All Applications

Deploying machine learning models in the cloud-edge continuum requires a systematic approach to managing the entire model lifecycle, ensuring scalability, and optimizing the inference process. Key tools and platforms such as MLflow are indispensable for overseeing the lifecycle of models, from experimentation to deployment. Seldon Core facilitates the deployment of these models as microservices within Kubernetes environments, allowing for scalable and resilient operations. Secure storage solutions like Amazon S3 are critical for safeguarding model data, while NVIDIA Triton Inference Server is pivotal for delivering optimized, high-performance inferencing across diverse hardware configurations.

In this integrated ecosystem, Kubernetes clusters play a crucial role by processing real-time performance data, which informers then use to accurately forecast future system states. These forecasts feed into a decision engine that dynamically adjusts system parameters to optimize performance, ensuring both continuous operation and efficiency. This strategic use of predictive analytics not only enhances system efficiency but also improves responsiveness, aligning with the overarching goal of maximizing user satisfaction across the cloud-edge continuum.

V. CONCLUSION

This article has been a first attempt to shed light on the potential benefits that the attention mechanisms can bring in the fast-growing area of cloud and edge computing. We have provided a comprehensive overview on the existing time-series forecasting techniques, focusing particularly on a new class of machine learning algorithms (i.e., informers) that employ a sparse attention mechanism to capture long-term connections with low complexity. Our proof-of-concept results have demonstrated that informers can provide improvements in prediction accuracy compared to traditional LSTM models, whilst delivering similar and low-complexity performance to transformers. Finally, we provided a list of cloud-edge related use cases for 5G and beyond ecosystems.

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